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Species sheet – All about rabbits!

Popular as pets, domestic rabbits are now commonplace in French households. This new species sheet, following on from the one on horses, is an opportunity to revisit the characteristics and needs of rabbits!

This species sheet was developed with Mélina Lattari and reviewed by Samuel Boucher, veterinarian and member of Labovet Conseil, Laura Warin, animal welfare project manager at ITAVI, and Chantal Davoust, head of France LAPIN and Basse cour within the ADM.

Sensory abilities

Sight

Panoramic field of view (almost 360°).
Rabbits cannot see under their chin.

Rabbits cannot see in total darkness but have better night vision than humans.

They can only see two colors clearly: **blue** and **green**. Their vision is sensitive to **light** and **movement**.

Smell

Their sense of smell is used for **communication** (marking, urine, feces), **exploration** (searching for and selecting food) and also for **locating and avoiding predators**.

DID YOU KNOW?

Rabbits have 50 to 100 times more olfactory receptors than humans!

Like most mammals, rabbits have a **vomerinal** organ that allows them to detect **pheromones**.

Cognitive abilities

Able to **distinguish** between individuals (rabbits, domestic carnivores, predators, and humans).

Able to respond to hand signs.

Taste

Can recognize salty, sweet, sour, and bitter flavors, with a preference for **sweet** and **bitter**.

DID YOU KNOW?

Rabbits like carrots, which are very high in sugars. They can be given as treats, but only in moderation!

Hearing

Rabbits can hear **ultrasound**. They are very sensitive to noise.

To accurately **locate** the source of a sound, rabbits **stand upright** on their hind legs with their ears extended.

Touch

To "touch", rabbits mainly use their **whiskers**, located around their nose and above their eyes.

Touch sensitivity

Most sensitive area

Thermal sensitivity*

Rabbit

Baby rabbit

*Rabbits' thermal comfort depends on their coat type (hairless, rex, very dense, or long), and their perception of temperature is influenced by humidity and air speed.